
GP referral / eligibility criteria for the CST

CNS

- Your patient has type 2 diabetes and is on two or more glycaemic agents at maximum tolerated doses and glycaemic control remains out of target.
- You require initiation of insulin or GLP1 for a patient with Type 2 Diabetes.
- You require a review of the patients' insulin regimen.
- You are concerned about a patient with type 2 diabetes who is a regular attendee to A&E with acute diabetes episodes.
- You are concerned about hypoglycaemic unawareness and recurrent hypoglycaemia in a patient with type 2 diabetes.
- Your patient has type 1 diabetes and has defaulted from the secondary care service.

Podiatrist

- Your patient has type 2 diabetes or type 1 diabetes and has been categorised on screening as moderate or high risk for diabetic foot disease (including those who have had a previous foot ulcer/amputation)

Dietitian

- Your patient has type 2 diabetes and elevated HbA1c and would like information and support regarding dietary modification and lifestyle management of type 2 diabetes
- Your patient has been diagnosed as having pre-diabetes and would like information and support on lifestyle modifications to prevent progression to type 2 diabetes
- Your patient has type 2 diabetes and would like support with weight management
- Your patient has type 2 diabetes and has cardiovascular risk factors such as hypertension or dyslipidaemia
- Your patient has type 2 diabetes and has impaired renal function

*Note: on diagnosis of type 2 diabetes, patients should be referred by their GP to a local structured diabetes education programme and encouraged to attend.
